

The Dual Role of Vitamin C Against Pseudomonas aeruginosa: A Systematic Review of Mechanisms and Antibiotic Interactions – Additional Materials

SOCIAL BACKGROUND

The concept of vitamins was introduced in 1913 by the Polish biochemist Kazimierz Funk. Over the subsequent 112 years, a B-complex, Vitamin C, and fat-soluble vitamins were described. As research on vitamins progressed, voices emerged regarding their therapeutic potential, that was often linked to the administration of exaggerated doses. Those who advocated for vitamin doses significantly exceeding the Recommended Dietary Allowance (RDA) include:

- Linus Pauling: With his 1968 publication in *Science*, he coined the term "orthomolecular medicine" [1], which is based on the premise that providing the body with appropriate doses of vitamins, micro- and macroelements is a crucial aspect of treatment. He also published books dedicated to combating, among other things, colds, flu, and cancer with Vitamin C. To this day, the Pauling Institute upholds the position on the therapeutic potential of megadoses of vitamins.
- Abram Hoffer: His work primarily focused on treating schizophrenia using megadoses of niacin. In 1962, he published a text summarizing nine years of his analyses and research, in which he indicated that gram doses of niacin supported the treatment of psychiatric patients and shortened the duration of therapy [2].
- Robert Cathcart: He promoted megadoses of Vitamin C. One of his more popular articles was a protocol for determining oral Vitamin C dosage tolerance from 1981. In it, he promoted doses exceeding 200g, for instance, in viral pneumonia, and suggested a correlation between increasing bowel tolerance and advancing disease severity [3].
- Frederick Klenner: As early as 1948, he published a text suggesting the treatment of viral pneumonia with Vitamin C, in which he described administering 2 to 4 grams of Vitamin C intravenously [4]. In his subsequent works, he discussed, among other things, the treatment of polio virus with Vitamin C [5].

The idea of high-dose vitamins is still propagated within the field of natural medicine / altmed, which stands in opposition to typical clinical practice (Evidence-Based Medicine - EBM). However, this does not mean that academic medicine (EBM) excludes the use of elevated vitamin doses; rather, they are a supplementary element to basic therapies.

On the international publishing market, there are books dedicated to the use of vitamins for treating various ailments, such as "Doctor Yourself: Natural Healing That Works" by Andrew W. Saul or "Ukryte terapie. Czego Ci lekarz nie powie" (Hidden Therapies. What Your Doctor Won't Tell You) by Jerzy Zięba. Jerzy Zięba is an example of an author who does not have specialized medical education, as he graduated with a degree in mining machinery.

The dietary supplement market, including preparations containing vitamins, is a prosperous sector. This directly stems from the demand for vitamin products. According to a Statista report [6], as many as 80% of Poles admitted to taking vitamin supplements within the last 12 months, which is the highest percentage among the surveyed countries. Among European countries, the United Kingdom ranked second with a result equal to that of the USA – 68%. A CDC analysis for the years 2017-18 also indicates a high percentage of people taking dietary supplements, with seniors leading at 74.3% compared to an overall average of 57.6% [7].

Unauthorized treatment methods using high doses of vitamins became popularized during the COVID-19 pandemic, i.e., in 2020-2022. Given that Poland ranks first in the popularity of consuming dietary supplements, the focus was placed on statistical data specifically from Poland. Poland is characterized by widespread internet access (the average percentage of households with internet access in 2020 was 90.4%), a high percentage of people using the internet to search for information about the pandemic (the average percentage of such individuals was 68.5% of respondents), and access to a wide selection of information sources, all of which led to polarization in society [8]. Google Trends data indicate a worldwide increase in interest in vitamins at the beginning of the pandemic and shortly after the introduction of vaccinations.

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Figure 1 - data obtained from Google Trends for the topic of Vitamins.

A study by Wróblewski et al. involving 1,000 Polish respondents indicates that Poles consider their close relatives to be the most trusted source of information, with "friends and acquaintances" and "doctors" yielding identical results [9].

These trends thus favored the popularization of mainly unconfirmed COVID-19 treatment methods. However, there are also grounds to believe that the topic of alternative medicine and vitamins has also gained popularity.

Figure 2 - data obtained from Google Trends for phrases: 'Jerzy Zięba' and his company 'Visanto'.

Previous popular science analyses, including those of Jerzy Zięba's texts, have shown that claims appearing in alternative medicine books are not entirely false, but rather manipulative [10,11]. We consider it essential to verify the theses put forward by proponents of alternative treatment methods against current medical literature and to determine whether it is justified to conduct more in-depth research on a given topic.

This review focuses on verifying a selected thesis put forward by individuals promoting alternative medicine.

VITAMIN C

Vitamin C is currently utilized in two primary forms: ascorbic acid and its salts, such as sodium ascorbate. For humans, it serves as a crucial antioxidant with a broad spectrum of action.

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Its most well-known function is its role in collagen synthesis, where it maintains iron ions in lysine and proline hydroxylases at a specific oxidation state. This prevents the auto-activation of these enzymes, thereby protecting against the formation of weak, immature collagen forms [13]. Furthermore, due to its antioxidant potential, it can protect lipids from peroxidation, regulate gene expression, and influence cell differentiation.

Figures 3 - ascorbic acid and dehydroascorbate (DHA)

The basic, neutral form of ascorbic acid, at pH = 7, tends to deprotonate into the (mono)anion ascorbate form, and in an acidic environment, undergoes secondary deprotonation to the ascorbate dianion. Ascorbic acid can be oxidized by both the human body and food processing to form dehydroascorbate (DHA) [14]. The conversions of ascorbic acid to DHA are reversible; the regeneration of ascorbic acid involves interaction with vitamin E or glutathione via a redox reaction [15].

Figure 4 - schematic interaction between vitamins: C, E, and glutathione (GSSG - oxidized form of glutathione)

Due to a mutation in the *GULO* gene (responsible for the oxidase that completes Vitamin C biosynthesis in the body), humans, like many other primates, cannot synthesize Vitamin C and must therefore obtain it through their diet [16]. NIH recommendations suggest that a daily supplementation of 90 mg is sufficient for adult men [17]. It's challenging to definitively determine the maximum plasma concentration of Vitamin C with oral supplementation versus intravenous infusions, as studies show inconsistent values. A 2004 study indicates that administering just 1.25g of Vitamin C intravenously can achieve concentrations 6 times higher than the maximum from oral supplementation. Furthermore, concentrations of nearly 16 mM are possible with hyperdoses of 100g via IV infusion [18]. However, data from another study suggest that achievable plasma concentrations can be as high as 27 mM in a healthy person given 75g of ascorbic acid intravenously, and 28 mM in an oncology patient given just 25g intravenously [19].

The human body is capable of secondary absorption of Vitamin C from urine, with the reabsorption level depending on the Vitamin C concentration in the body; it occurs more intensely in oncology patients. Excretion happens via urine, and the concentration of the vitamin in excreted urine increases with the administered dose [20]. The half-life ($T_{1/2}$) of Vitamin C is variable and can be as long as 40 days in cases of severe dietary deficiency. Otherwise, when its plasma concentration exceeds 70 μM , this period shortens to 30 minutes [21].

The absorption of Vitamin C by mammalian cells primarily relies on SVCT transporters, but the Vitamin can also be absorbed via GLUT transporters. When it comes to dietary supplementation, bioavailability is a crucial parameter. As indicated by the German Nutrition Society (DGE), a daily dose of up to 100 mg of ascorbic acid has a bioavailability of 80%, but for doses around 1250 mg, this parameter no longer exceeds 50% [22] - thus,

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bioavailability is inversely proportional to the orally administered dose of ascorbic acid. For this reason, when implementing oral supplementation, maintaining high bioavailability regardless of the dose used would be important.

The development of nanotechnology has allowed for the creation of methods for forming nanoemulsions with vitamins. Therefore, considering the use of ascorbic acid salts or encapsulating the vitamin in a liposomal form might lead to improved bioavailability, as noted by Dickerson et al. in the introduction to their study [23]. Nano-forms of vitamins can improve, among other things, stability, antioxidant properties, and support collagen synthesis [24].

PSEUDOMONAS AERUGINOSA

Pseudomonas is a genus of Gram-negative bacteria with broad industrial applications, including biogas production [25,26] and insecticide degradation [27]. However, the species *P. aeruginosa* is highly pathogenic to humans. Sources indicate that in Poland, *P. aeruginosa* may account for as many as 10% of hospital-acquired infections [28]. These cultures can develop in the respiratory and urinary tracts, as well as in areas of skin damage [29]. In dermatological infections, particularly those affecting nails, *P. aeruginosa* causes characteristic green discoloration. This symptom results from *P. aeruginosa*'s production of various pigments: pyocyanin, pyoverdine (fluorescein), pyorubin, or pyomelanin.

These pigments have specific roles and properties. For example, up to 95% of *P. aeruginosa* strains produce pyocyanin, which is responsible for the blue-green coloration of colonies. In the context of pathogenicity, this pigment plays a significant role by, among other things, interacting with extracellular DNA (eDNA, exDNA) to form robust biofilms and controlling the expression of genes encoding efflux pumps. The production of pigments, including pyocyanin, can be regulated by the Quorum Sensing system, described below. Although pyocyanin increases the competitiveness of *P. aeruginosa* due to its antibacterial and antifungal properties, in excessive amounts, it can negatively affect *P. aeruginosa* cells by generating reactive oxygen species (ROS) [30].

Due to its antibiotic resistance and pathogenicity, *P. aeruginosa* is a frequent subject of research interest. *P. aeruginosa* exhibits significant internal diversity. Among the most common strains are PAO1 and PA14; these strains are well-characterized, and their genomes are fully sequenced, making them typical research subjects. One of the characteristic differences between these strains is that PA14 is distinguished by higher virulence compared to PAO1; due to its physiology, this strain is excellent material for studies on biofilm formation [31]. One reason for differences in virulence may be different gene expression, which directly impacts the function of the Quorum Sensing (QS) system [32].

P. aeruginosa possesses several mechanisms that allow it to combat and compete with other bacterial species; one of these is the QS system. QS can be divided into the *las* and *rhl* systems. The former, through the synthesis of 3-oxo-C12-HSL, influences the expression of genes responsible for: elastase B (*lasB* gene), protease *lasA* (*lasA* gene), exotoxin A (*toxA* gene), or alkaline metalloprotease (*apr* gene). The *rhl* system, in turn, is responsible for the expression of genes necessary for the synthesis of rhamnolipids, which are compounds with biosurfactant and hemolytic properties, though their exact role remains undetermined to this day [33]. However, it is known that rhamnolipids can exhibit antibacterial activity against other species, thus potentially complementing *P. aeruginosa*'s systems for combating other species.

P. aeruginosa is characterized by its ability to efficiently develop resistance to common antibiotics. Increasing resistance to widely used antibiotics, even when combined with other compounds, has been reported for many years [34]. One such antibiotic is neomycin, found in popular over-the-counter antibacterial ointments in Poland. The high reported percentage of strains causing infections that are resistant to carbapenems is also alarming; Tenover et al. cite that the percentage of carbapenem-resistant clinical isolates in the USA can be as high as 30%. They also indicate that the basis for broad resistance to β -lactams may include: the MexAB-OprM pump, decreased frequency of the OprD transport protein, and increased production of AmpC β -lactamases, including carbapenemases. It is worth noting that carbapenem-resistant strains may additionally possess genes conferring resistance to β -lactamase inhibitors, fluoroquinolones, and aminoglycosides [35].

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In 2017, the World Health Organization (WHO) published a list of bacterial families posing the greatest threat to human health; *P. aeruginosa* was placed in the priority group, named "Critical" [36]. This fact is not surprising, given that *P. aeruginosa* can lead to bacteremia with high mortality rates [37], and as previously noted, broad resistance significantly increases the risk of treatment failure, even with the strongest antibiotics.

CURRENT THERAPIES

The precise choice of antibiotic for *P. aeruginosa* infections depends on the infection site. In the Polish pharmaceutical market, over-the-counter ointments typically consist of three antibiotics: Bacitracin, Neomycin, and Polymyxin. There are also cases where doctors mistakenly prescribe antibiotics, such as fusidic acid, which is a steroid antibiotic ineffective against *P. aeruginosa*.

The Polish initiative under the Ministry of Health, the "Narodowy Program Ochrony Antybiotyków" in its 2020 recommendations, suggests treating various forms of *P. aeruginosa* infections with antibiotics like: Piperacillin-Tazobactam, Ceftazidime, Cefepime, Ceftolozane-Tazobactam, Imipenem/Meropenem, Aztreonam, Gentamicin, Ciprofloxacin, and Levofloxacin [38]. These recommendations align with the latest CLSI 2024 guidelines.

Studies included in this review utilized antibiotics from several distinct groups, briefly characterized below [39]:

- β -lactams: These antibiotics possess a characteristic β -lactam ring in their structure. Their primary mechanism of action involves covalently binding to penicillin-binding proteins (PBPs). This prevents the cross-linking of adjacent peptide chains, which is essential for the complete synthesis of peptidoglycan (a key component of bacterial cell walls).
- Aminoglycosides: Their fundamental mechanism involves interacting with ribosomes, leading to errors in translation. This results in the formation of faulty proteins, including membrane proteins.
- Fluoroquinolones: These interact with enzymes crucial for DNA replication: gyrase and topoisomerase IV. This ultimately leads to the halting of new DNA synthesis.
- Tetracyclines: These interact with ribosomal subunits, preventing the attachment of tRNA to the A-site of the ribosome. This, in turn, leads to the inhibition of protein synthesis.

REFERENCES

1. Pauling L. Orthomolecular Psychiatry: Varying the concentrations of substances normally present in the human body may control mental disease. *Science*. 1968;160:265–71.
2. Osmond H, Hoffer A. MASSIVE NIACIN TREATMENT IN SCHIZOPHRENIA. *The Lancet*. 1962;279:316–20.
3. Cathcart RF. Vitamin C, TITRATING TO BOWEL TOLERANCE, ANASCORBEMIA, and ACUTE INDUCED SCURVY. *Med Hypotheses*. 1981;7:1359–76.
4. FRED R. KLENNER. Virus Pneumonia and Its Treatment With Vitamin C. *South Med Surg*. 1948;
5. Fred R. Klenner. The Treatment of Poliomyelitis and Other Virus Diseases with Vitamin C. *J South Med Surg*. 1949;
6. Infographic: Who's Taking Their Vitamins? [Internet]. Stat. Dly. Data. 2024 [cited 2025 Jun 6]. Available from: <https://www.statista.com/chart/28649/share-of-people-that-take-vitamins-in-europe>
7. Products - Data Briefs - Number 399 - February 2021 [Internet]. 2021 [cited 2025 Jun 6]. Available from: <https://www.cdc.gov/nchs/products/databriefs/db399.htm>
8. GUS. Społeczeństwo informacyjne w Polsce w 2020 r. [Internet]. Available from: <https://stat.gov.pl/obszary-tematyczne/nauka-i-technika-spoleczenstwo-informacyjne/spoleczenstwo-informacyjne/spoleczenstwo-informacyjne-w-polsce-w-2020-roku,1,14.html>
9. Wróblewski, Michał; Meler, Andrzej; Afeltowicz, Łukasz. Ryzyko, zaufanie, choroby zakaźne. Polki i Polacy o pandemii [Internet]. [cited 2024 Nov 28]. Available from: <https://repozytorium.umk.pl/handle/item/6434>

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10. Sakowski Ł. Jerzy Zięba nominowany do Biologicznej Bzdury Roku 2024 [Internet]. Tylko Teor. 2024 [cited 2025 Jun 6]. Available from: <https://www.totylkoteoria.pl/jerzy-zieba-biologiczna-bzdura/>
11. Blogger naukowy wygrał proces z Jerzym Ziębą [Internet]. [cited 2025 Jun 6]. Available from: <https://www.termedia.pl/wartowiedziec/Blogger-naukowy-wygral-proces-z-Jerzym-Zieba,50137.html>
12. Rawal BD. Bactericidal Action of Ascorbic Acid on Pseudomonas aeruginosa: Alteration of Cell Surface as a Possible Mechanism. Chemotherapy. 1978;24:166–71.
13. Boyera N, Galey I, Bernard BA. Effect of vitamin C and its derivatives on collagen synthesis and cross-linking by normal human fibroblasts. Int J Cosmet Sci. 1998;20:151–8.
14. Figueroa-Méndez R, Rivas-Arancibia S. Vitamin C in Health and Disease: Its Role in the Metabolism of Cells and Redox State in the Brain. Front Physiol [Internet]. 2015 [cited 2025 Jan 11];6. Available from: <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/physiology/articles/10.3389/fphys.2015.00397/full>
15. Pullar JM, Carr AC, Vissers MCM. The Roles of Vitamin C in Skin Health. Nutrients. 2017;9:866.
16. Hongwen Yang. Conserved or Lost: Molecular Evolution of the Key Gene GULO in Vertebrate Vitamin C Biosynthesis. Biochem Genet [Internet]. 2013 [cited 2024 Dec 5];51. Available from: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10528-013-9574-0>
17. National Institutes of Health. Vitamin C Fact Sheet for Health Professionals [Internet]. [cited 2024 Dec 5]. Available from: <https://ods.od.nih.gov/factsheets/VitaminC-HealthProfessional/>
18. Padayatty SJ, Sun H, Wang Y, Riordan HD, Hewitt SM, Katz A, et al. Vitamin C Pharmacokinetics: Implications for Oral and Intravenous Use. Ann Intern Med. 2004;140:533–7.
19. Chen P, Reed G, Jiang J, Wang Y, Sunega J, Dong R, et al. Pharmacokinetic Evaluation of Intravenous Vitamin C: A Classic Pharmacokinetic Study. Clin Pharmacokinet. 2022;61:1237–49.
20. Jens Lykkesfeldt i inni. The Pharmacokinetics of Vitamin C. [cited 2024 Dec 5]; Available from: <https://www.mdpi.com/2072-6643/11/10/2412>
21. Jorge Duconge i inni. Pharmacokinetics of vitamin C: Insights into the oral and intravenous administration of ascorbate. 2008 [cited 2024 Dec 5];PRHSJ Vol. 27 No. 1. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/5402680_Pharmacokinetics_of_vitamin_C_Insights_into_the_oral_and_intravenous_administration_of_ascorbate
22. German Nutrition Society (DGE). New Reference Values for Vitamin C Intake. Ann Nutr Metab. 2015;67:13–20.
23. Dickerson B, Gonzalez DE, Sowinski R, Xing D, Leonard M, Kendra J, et al. Comparative Effectiveness of Ascorbic Acid vs. Calcium Ascorbate Ingestion on Pharmacokinetic Profiles and Immune Biomarkers in Healthy Adults: A Preliminary Study. Nutrients. 2024;16:3358.
24. Bedhiafi T, Idoudi S, Fernandes Q, Al-Zaidan L, Uddin S, Dermime S, et al. Nano-vitamin C: A promising candidate for therapeutic applications. Biomed Pharmacother. 2023;158:114093.
25. Agnieszka Montusiewicz. Methods for Enhancing Biogas Production. Routledge;
26. Buettner C, von Bergen M, Jehmlich N, Noll M. Pseudomonas spp. are key players in agricultural biogas substrate degradation. Sci Rep. 2019;9:12871.
27. Liu H, Chen W-J, Xu Z, Chen S-F, Song H, Huang Y, et al. Unraveling the degradation mechanism of multiple pyrethroid insecticides by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and its environmental bioremediation potential. Environ Int. 2025;195:109221.

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28. Zakażenia pałeczką ropy błękitnej [Internet]. [cited 2025 Feb 10]. Available from: <http://www.mp.pl/social/article/163999>
29. Schwartz B, Klamer K, Zimmerman J, Kale-Pradhan PB, Bhargava A. Multidrug Resistant *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* in Clinical Settings: A Review of Resistance Mechanisms and Treatment Strategies. *Pathogens*. 2024;13:975.
30. Abdelaziz AA, Kamer AMA, Al-Monofy KB, Al-Madboly LA. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*'s greenish-blue pigment pyocyanin: its production and biological activities. *Microb Cell Factories*. 2023;22:110.
31. LaBauve AE, Wargo MJ. Growth and Laboratory Maintenance of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. *Curr Protoc Microbiol* [Internet]. 2012 [cited 2025 Feb 10];25. Available from: <https://currentprotocols.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/9780471729259.mc06e01s25>
32. Sana TG, Lomas R, Gimenez MR, Laubier A, Soscia C, Chauvet C, et al. Differential Modulation of Quorum Sensing Signaling through QslA in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* Strains PAO1 and PA14. *J Bacteriol*. 2019;201:10.1128/jb.00362-19.
33. Pearson JP, Pesci EC, Iglewski BH. Roles of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* las and rhl quorum-sensing systems in control of elastase and rhamnolipid biosynthesis genes. *J Bacteriol*. 1997;179:5756–67.
34. Cantrell HF, Lombardy EE, Duncanson FP, Katz E, Barone JS. Declining susceptibility to neomycin and polymyxin B of pathogens recovered in otitis externa clinical trials. *South Med J*. 2004;97:465–71.
35. Tenover FC, Nicolau DP, Gill CM. Carbapenemase-producing *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* –an emerging challenge. *Emerg Microbes Infect*. 2022;11:811–4.
36. WHO publishes list of bacteria for which new antibiotics are urgently needed [Internet]. [cited 2024 Dec 22]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/news/item/27-02-2017-who-publishes-list-of-bacteria-for-which-new-antibiotics-are-urgently-needed>
37. Babich T, Naucler P, Valik JK, Giske CG, Benito N, Cardona R, et al. Risk factors for mortality among patients with *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* bacteraemia: a retrospective multicentre study. *Int J Antimicrob Agents*. 2020;55:105847.
38. Szpitalna-lista-antybiotyków-2020.pdf [Internet]. [cited 2025 Feb 13]. Available from: <https://antybiotyki.edu.pl/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/Szpitalna-lista-antybiotyk%C3%B3w-2020.pdf>
39. Baran A, Kwiatkowska A, Potocki L. Antibiotics and Bacterial Resistance—A Short Story of an Endless Arms Race. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2023;24:5777.